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Time Series Analysis Of Oil Revenue And Poverty Level In Nigeria: An ARDL Approach

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ABSTRACT

Oil revenue holds potential for poverty reduction by financing transport infrastructures, healthcare, and education. The study examined time series analysis of oil revenue and poverty level in Nigeria: an ARDL Approach from 1982 to 2023. In order to achieve this, descriptive statistics, unit root test, bound co-integration, and ARDL estimation method were employed to analyze the data. The study found that Oil Revenue (OREV) reduces Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria in the short run but increases poverty level in the long run in Nigeria. The coefficient of Oil Revenue (OREV) do not impacts significantly on Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria both in the short run and in the long run; Inflation (INFR) increases Poverty level (POVR) both in the short run and in the long run in Nigeria but do not impact significantly on it; Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) increases Poverty level (POVR) both in the short run and in the long run in Nigeria but do not impact significantly on it; Corruption Perception Index (COPI) reduces Poverty level (POVR) both in the short run and in the long run in Nigeria but do not impact significantly on it; and Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) reduces Poverty level (POVR) both in the short run and in the long run in Nigeria but do not impact significantly on it. The study therefore concludes that oil revenue increases poverty level in Nigeria in the long run within the period under review. The study therefore recommends that government should diversify the Economy by investing in Non-Oil Sectors. That is strengthen agriculture, manufacturing, and technology to reduce dependence on oil revenue. Government should support Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) by providing incentives, training, and financial support to diversify income sources for citizens.

Keywords: Oil, Oil Revenue, Poverty, Poverty Level, Unit Root, ARDL

INTRODUCTION

Oil revenue has remained the live wire of Nigeria's economy given that it contributes over 80 percent to the nation's foreign exchange earnings and more than 50 percent to her gross domestic product (Chijioke & Olisah, 2023). The Nigerian economy is one which a layman will expect to be among the best in the world, as well as seeing an average Nigerian living above the poverty level. The nation is endowed with different mineral and land resources. The quantity of the deposits of such resources is expected to have changed the pattern, behavior and status of Nigeria as a country. Almost every state in Nigeria has more than three natural resources which if developed can generate sufficient revenue to tackle poverty in the land. Adelowokan and Osoba (2015), opined that oil income being the principal source of revenue in Nigeria ought to have more tangible impact in guaranteeing equal distribution of income as way of decreasing poverty rate among her residents. Notwithstanding, they discovered that the oil revenue is not utilized in the right direction and this has exacerbated the poverty level in Nigeria.

Available data show that Nigeria has about 31.4 percent of Africa's proven oil reserve and about 1.97 percent of world's oil reserve. The oil industry has generated enormous financial resources as it was estimated that between 1958 and June, 2016 that about #96.21 trillion was generated as federal government revenue from oil (Nweke & Elem, 2017).

Despite this oil wealth, Nigeria which was rated as one of the fifty richest nations globally in the early 1970s, drastically nose-dived to become the poverty headquarter of the world.

Literature Review Oil Revenue

Oil revenue is simply defined as the money gotten from the sale of crude oil. The Nigerian government revenue can be divided into two main headings; the oil revenue and the non-oil revenue. Oil is the main source where government generates more income, public finances and foreign exchange reserve. According to NEITI (2016) reports, 37.2 billion of oil reserve barrels were available in 2013 of which larger percent was sent to the USA thereby making Nigeria to become the 4th largest oil supplying nation in the world to USA.

The Concept of Poverty

The concept of poverty is multifaceted which includes social, economic and political elements. Absolute and relative forms of poverty are the most common. The absolute occurs when people lack means of getting necessary basic needs such as food, clothing and shelter while relative poverty is described as a situation which occurs when people in a country do not enjoy a certain minimum level of living standards as compared to the rest of the nations.

Theoretical Literature

The Principle of Maximum Social Advantage

The Principle of Maximum Social Advantage was developed by an Economist, Hugh Dalton. According to Dalton, public finance is concerned with government revenue and expenditures and their overlapping activities. This principle is considered to be the fundamental principle of public finance because it explains that the revenue collected by the government through taxation and any other means and the dispersal of public expenditures can have significant impact on the consumption, production and distribution of the national income of the nation. The government through its fiscal policy and intervention programs transfers from the central government to the populace. The fiscal activities have effects on level of income, output and employment in the country.

The principle of maximum social advantage implies that government spending is subject to diminishing marginal social benefits and revenues are subject to increasing marginal social costs. Thus, equilibrium is reached when social advantage is maximized, i.e., when the size of the budget is such that marginal social benefits of public expenditures are equal to the marginal social sacrifice.

Dalton emphasizes that government spending in every sector of the economy should be carried just so far, that the advantage to the community of a further small increase in any direction is just counter-balanced by the disadvantage of a corresponding small increase in taxation or in receipts from any other sources of public expenditure and public income. This theory indicates that before government can generate any revenue from any source i.e., in form of taxation or sales of its natural resources, there must be some sacrifice from the area where the revenue is sourced from or the payers of the tax, hence, there is maximum social advantage when those who suffered the payment or affected by extraction of resources derive benefits from the activities of government which are passed on to them through government spending. He called the sacrifice rendered by the populace towards the payment of taxes to the government or pollution effects received as a result of exploration of natural resources as Maximum Social Sacrifice (MSS) while the benefits derived from the government spending towards social and economic growth and development, poverty alleviation programs and empowerment services as Maximum social Benefit (MSB).

Empirical Literature Review

Imeokparia et al (2023) studied a panel analysis of crude oil exports and poverty reduction in African oil producing countries implications for the sustainable development goal one. The study spanned over 30 years, from 1991 to 2020, and relied on secondary data extracted from ten (10) highest oil-producing countries in Africa. The Human development index (HDI) was used as a proxy for poverty reduction. The panel ARDL technique was used to analyze the data. The findings revealed that oil exports using revenues from oil exportation and total annual barrels of oil produced had a beneficial impact on human capital development and thus reduced poverty in the selected African oil-exporting countries.

Chijioke & Olisah (2023) studied oil revenue and poverty in Nigeria: the South-South perspective in

post covid-19 era. Using a descriptive approach and data obtained from the World Bank and National Bureau of statistics, the study revealed an independent relationship between oil revenue and the rate of poverty in the region.

Panotani (2022) studied an empirical analysis of the impact of oil revenue on poverty reduction in Nigeria: an ARDL Bound Test for co-integration Approach. The study examined the impact of oil revenue in Nigeria and its effect on poverty rate from 1992 to 2019. The findings revealed that a percentage increase in oil revenue is statistically significant in reducing poverty by about 0.96%. This indicates that oil revenue is significant in reducing the poverty rate in Nigeria.

Ewubare & Uzoma (2019) studied oil revenue and economic growth: an empirical evidence stochastic characteristics of each time series was tested using Augmented Dickey-Fuller test. The ARDL Model was used to estimate the coefficients of the parameters for both the short-run and the long-run. Findings from the study showed that in the long-run, oil revenue and oil rent impacted on GDP positively although not significantly. In the short-run however, both variable retarded economic growth in Nigeria.

Nweke & Eleme (2017) studied oil wealth dependable and poverty in Nigeria, focusing on socioeconomic and infrastructural induced poverty. The study discovered lack of access to socio-economic and infrastructural facilities, weak institutional arrangements, poor governance, and neglect of other sectors and sub-sectors of the economy including manufacturing sectors, and lack of transparency, etc, as reasons why the people have continued to remain in object poverty in the midst of abundant oil wealth.

Rahmon (2019) studied the effects of oil revenue on poverty reduction in Nigeria. Collecting time series data mainly sourced from the database of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), the study employed the econometrics analysis of Multiple Linear regressions, Pair-wise Granger-Causality and descriptive statistics. The regression results reveal that oil revenue has short run insignificant effects on poverty reduction. Also, it was discovered that a bidirectional causality exists between the two variables.

Bala & Chin (2018) employed dynamic panels ARDL to measure the oil price shocks on inflation rate in Algeria, Angola, Libya and Nigeria. They concluded that increase of oil prices lead to higher inflation rate for those countries.

Nwoba & Abah (2018) examined the impact of crude oil revenue on the growth of the Nigerian economy from (1960-2010), proposed two specific objectives. The findings revealed the extent of economic growth impacted by the oil industries was significant based on the ordinary least square (OLS) regression analysis result where the calculated F-Statistics of (212.1293) is greater than the tabulated F-statistics of (5.35147). The study also found the long run positive relationship between oil revenue and gross domestic product.

Folami (2017) examined the effects of oil revenue on poverty reduction in Nigeria. The aim was to evaluate the contribution of oil revenue on poverty level, to determine whether oil revenue is a good predictor of poverty reduction in Nigeria and to establish whether any form of directional causality exists between the two variables? The regression results revealed that oil revenue has short run insignificant effects on poverty reduction. Also, it was discovered that a bi-directional causality exists between the two variables.

Zhao (2016) implemented dynamic stochastic general equilibrium method to investigate effect of oil price on CPI. The result showed that oil supply shocks lead to long-term inflation in China's economy.

Asogwa & Okpongette (2015) carried out a study to ascertain the effects of oil revenue on the macroeconomic performance of Nigeria. This study made use of data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the World Bank from 1981 to 2014. The Ordinary Least Squared (OLS) technique and the Granger Causality test were used to ascertain the effect of oil revenue on Nigeria macroeconomic performance. The result shows that oil revenue is statistically significant with economic growth in Nigeria and a positive relationship exists between them. Co-integration result shows evidence of long run relationship between oil revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. However, the result of Granger causality test shows that oil revenue does not cause Economic growth.

Adelowokan & Osoba (2015) examined the impact of revenue from oil proceeds and disaggregated government spending on poverty rate in Nigeria. The result revealed that gross domestic product and revenue from oil proceeds exert negative effect on Poverty rate in Nigeria during the reviewed

period.

Usman, Madu & Abdullahu (2015) carried out a study titled Evidence of Petroleum sources on Nigerian Economic Development (2000-2009). The main objective of the study was to examine the impact of petroleum on Nigeria's economic development. The data used was a ten years record of GDP and Oil Revenue, 2000-2009. The tool of analysis used was Simple Linear Regression Model with the aid of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS). The study found that petroleum has a direct and positive significant relationship with the economy.

Khalid & Azrai (2015) carried out studies on the effect of oil revenue on the Sudan economy, they discovered a causal relationship between oil revenue and the country GDP.

Their discovery indicates that a unit change in oil revenue will lead to 25% changes in the GDP. The argument earlier suggests that government expenditure be directed towards specific poverty reduction programmes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the ex-post facto research design in which secondary data were obtained from World Bank data bases and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) from 1981 to 2023.

Model Specification

The model for this study was adopted from the work of Imeokparia et al. (2023) but with some modifications in terms of variables as follows;

$$HDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 INN + \beta_2 GWT + \beta_3 EXP + \beta_4 POP + u \quad 1$$

However, for the purpose of this study, the model was adjusted to suit the objective of this study.

The functional relationship between oil revenue and poverty level can be expressed as:

$$POVR = f(OREV, INFR, GCEE, COPI, GCEH) \quad 2$$

The econometric form of the models is expressed as:

$$POVR = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 OREV + \beta_2 INFLR + \beta_3 GCEE + \beta_4 COPI + \beta_5 GCEH + \mu_1 \quad 3$$

Where:

α_0 = is the constant variable (or the intercept)

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = are the coefficients of the explanatory variables. μ_1 = is error term

POVR = Poverty Rate OREV = Oil Revenue

INFLR = Inflation Rate

GCEE = Government Capital Expenditure on Education COPI = Corruption Perception Index

GCEH = Government Capital Expenditure on Health

Apriori Expectations

$$\beta_1 < 0; \beta_2 > 0; \beta_3 < 0; \beta_4 > 0; \beta_5 < 0$$

Estimation Techniques

The variables in the study were subjected to unit root test so as to determine their degree of stationarity using the Augmented Dickey Fuller test. Based on the results of the unit root test, the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model was used in estimating the data. The ARDL bound test was based on the condition that the order of integration of the series is a mixture of both 1(0) and 1(1). The Error correction model was used to determine the short run behavior of the variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analyses of the data were done in phases. The first phase is the descriptive statistics to ascertain the behaviour of the variables. Secondly, is the unit root test followed by the ARDL modelling techniques and lastly the post estimation tests.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 below presents the result of the descriptive statistics of the variables employed in the estimations in this study.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	POVR	OREV	INFR	GCEE	COPI	GCEH
Mean	52.71302	2650.768	18.84095	177.0465	7.961508	107.9236
Median	53.50000	1890.922	12.94500	70.64108	1.680000	33.73399
Maximum	66.90000	8878.970	72.84000	702.9787	28.00000	437.5212
Minimum	39.10000	7.253000	5.390000	0.162154	0.000000	0.041315
Std. Dev.	7.388144	2635.911	16.45739	221.5453	11.27252	141.3438
Skewness	0.070404	0.576521	1.895991	1.104795	0.957606	1.162769
Kurtosis	2.272734	2.150979	5.484153	2.887274	1.980746	2.999621
Jarque-Bera	0.960301	3.588099	35.96276	8.566247	8.237102	9.464219
Probability	0.618690	0.166285	0.000000	0.013799	0.016268	0.008808
Sum	2213.947	111332.2	791.3200	7435.952	334.3833	4532.793
Sum Sq. Dev.	2237.972	2.85E+08	11104.67	2012375.	5209.863	819100.6
Observations	42	42	42	42	42	42

Source: Author's Computation (2024)

The result of the descriptive statistics in Table 1 shows that Poverty level (POVR) have a mean value of (3.381856) with a standard deviation of 3.741964. The skewness value of Poverty level (POVR) is positive (0.464316), meaning that Poverty level (POVR) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Poverty level (POVR) is 1.349218 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is leptokurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series are higher than the sample mean.

Oil Revenue (OREV) has a mean value of 0.364140 with a standard deviation of 0.286084. The skewness value of Oil Revenue (OREV) is positive (1.176838), meaning that Oil Revenue (OREV) has a long-left tail while the kurtosis value of Oil Revenue (OREV) is 3.728440 (i. e. greater than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a peak distribution, meaning that the series are higher than the sample mean.

Inflation (INFR) has a mean value of 46.38001 with a standard deviation of 5.552765. The skewness value of Inflation (INFR) is positive (0.217968), meaning that Inflation (INFR) has a long-right tail while the kurtosis value of Inflation (INFR) is 2.800430 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series are lower than the sample mean.

Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) has a mean value of 31.25695 with a standard deviation of 12.28472. The skewness value of Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) is negative (-0.174001), meaning that Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) has a long-left tail while the kurtosis value of Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) is 2.107426 (i. e. less than 3), meaning that it is platykurtic. That is, it has a flat distribution, meaning that the series are lower than the sample mean.

Corruption Perception Index (COPI) has a mean value of 127.7389 with a standard deviation of 141.9315. The skewness value of Corruption Perception Index (COPI) is positive (1.515334), meaning that Corruption Perception Index (COPI) has a long-left tail while the kurtosis value of Corruption Perception Index (COPI) is 5.378110 (i. e. greater than 3), meaning that it is leptokurtic. That is, it has a peak distribution, meaning that the series are higher than the mean sample.

While Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) has a mean value of 127.7389 with a standard deviation of 141.9315. The skewness value of Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) is positive (1.515334), meaning that Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) has a long-left tail while the kurtosis value of Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) is 5.378110 (i. e. greater than 3), meaning that it is leptokurtic. That is, it has a peak distribution, meaning that the series are higher than the mean sample.

Based on these observations, it is therefore necessary to test for the stationarity of the variables and the long run relationship since using the variables at level might give a spurious result. The unit root test is conducted so as to make the variables stationary. The study adopts the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test procedure.

Unit Root Test

Tables 2 below presents result of stationarity test for each of variables used using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Results

Variables	ADF at Level	ADF at 1 st Difference	Status	Remarks
POVR	-2.190570	-7.528080	I(1)	Stationary
OREV	-1.557513	-6.619286	I(1)	Stationary
INFR	-3.674921	-	I(0)	Stationary
GCEE	1.280252	-5.376225	I(1)	Stationary
COPI	-0.813098	-7.250036	I(1)	Stationary
GCEH	0.757832	-7.096642	I(1)	Stationary
<i>Critical Values</i>				
1% level	-3.600987	-3.605593		
5% level	-2.935001	-2.936942		
10% level	-2.605836	-2.606857		

Source: *Author's Computation (2024)*

The outcomes of unit root test in Table 2 for the Model, reveals that INFR was stationary at level while POV, OREV, GCEE, COPI, and GCEH were stationary at 1st difference. Hence, the study then concludes that the independent variables used in model one were integrated of both order zero and one, that is I(1) and I(0) and the dependent variable is integrated of order one, that is, I(1). Since the ADF result indicates that the series are of different order of integration, we cannot use the Engle-Granger and Johansen co-integration tests but rather the appropriate test to use in this study is the Bounds co-integration test. According to Giles (1975), Perasan, Shin and Smith (2001), Jawaid and Waheed (2016) and Salisu (2016), when the series used in any study are of different order of co-integration, the appropriate test to use is the bound co-integration test.

(ii) Bound Test Co-Integration Result

The result of the Bound Co-integration test is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: ARDL Bound Test Co-integration Result for the Model

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	4.423490	5
<i>Critical Value Bounds</i>		
Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.26	3.35
5%	2.62	3.79
2.5%	2.96	4.18
1%	3.41	4.68

Source: *Author's Computation using E-view Software*

From Table 3, the result of the bound co-integration test shows that the calculated f-statistic value of 4.423490 falls higher than the theoretical critical value for the upper bound I(1) at 5 percent level. This means that there is a co-integration, hence, a long run relationship exists between POV, OREV, INFR, GCEE, COPI, and GCEH in Nigeria within the period under review. Since there is a long run relationship among the variables, we now proceed to estimate the short run dynamics and long run models based on the ARDL approach.

Table 4: ARDL Short Run Estimation Result for the model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DLOG(OREV)	-1.139340	2.174626	-0.523925	0.6038
D(INFR)	0.023490	0.047039	0.499368	0.6208
DLOG(GCEE)	2.912586	2.719067	1.071171	0.2919
D(COPI)	-0.056515	0.104606	-0.540269	0.5926
DLOG(GCEH)	-4.599170	2.860422	-1.607865	0.1174
ECM (-1)	-0.322656	0.120484	-2.678000	0.0115
R-squared = 0.535537; Adjusted R-squared = 0.523314; F-statistic = 43.81495 (Prob(F-statistic) = 0.000000; Durbin-Watson stat = 2.036429				

Source: Author's Computation using E-view Software

(iii) Short Run Estimation Results for the Model

Table 4 shows the estimated coefficients of the short run relationship between the variables in the model.

From Table 4, the result shows that the ECM included in this model has the right sign (i. e. negative) and is statistically significant at 5 percent level. The coefficient of the ECT is -0.322656, suggesting that almost 32 percent of discrepancy between the long run and short run is corrected within a year. This adjustment implies that about 32 per cent of errors are corrected within one year since that data were annual series. The ECM also reveals that a long run relationship exists between the regressors (OREV, INFR, GCEE, COPI, and GCEH) and the response variable (POVR) in this model. The findings confirmed that a short run relationship exist among the variables in the model.

Furthermore, the calculated Adj-R2 is 0.523314. This means that about 52 per cent of the total variations in Poverty level (POVR) are caused by the explanatory variables Oil Revenue (OREV), Inflation (INFR), Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE), Corruption Perception Index (COPI), and Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH). Thus, the remaining 48 per cent of variations is caused by exogenous factors to the model but covered by the error term. Also, the F-statistics calculated of 43.81495 with an F-stat probability value of 0.000000 which is less than 0.05 level, means that the overall model is significant at 5 per cent level. The value of the D.W is 2.036429 suggests that there is minimal serial autocorrelation in the model.

From Table 4, the result of the short run estimation shows that Oil Revenue (OREV) has a negative (-1.139340) relationship with Poverty level (POVR), suggesting that a unit increase in Oil Revenue (OREV) reduces Poverty level (POVR) by 1.139340 units in Nigeria. The negative effect of Oil Revenue (OREV) on Poverty level (POVR) confirm to a priori and therefore is in line with economic theory. The negative effect of Oil Revenue (OREV) on Poverty level (POVR) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Oil Revenue (OREV) and Poverty level (POVR).

Inflation (INFR) has a positive (0.023490) relationship with Poverty level (POVR), suggesting that a unit increase in Inflation (INFR) increases Poverty level (POVR) by 0.023490 units in Nigeria. The positive effect of Inflation (INFR) on Poverty level (POVR) confirm to a priori and therefore is in line with economic theory. The positive effect of Inflation (INFR) on Poverty level (POVR) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Inflation (INFR) and Poverty level (POVR).

Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) has a positive (2.912586) relationship with Poverty level (POVR), suggesting that a unit increase in Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) increases Poverty level (POVR) by 2.912586 units in Nigeria. The positive effect of Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) on Poverty level (POVR) do not confirm to a priori and therefore not in line with economic theory. The positive effect of Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) on Poverty level (POVR) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) and Poverty level (POVR).

Corruption Perception Index (COPI) has a negative (-0.056515) relationship with Poverty level

(POVR), suggesting that a unit increase in Corruption Perception Index (COPI) decreases Poverty level (POVR) by 0.056515 units in Nigeria. The negative effect of Corruption Perception Index (COPI) on Poverty level (POVR) do not confirm to a priori and therefore not in line with economic theory. The negative effect of Corruption Perception Index (COPI) on Poverty level (POVR) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Corruption Perception Index (COPI) and Poverty level (POVR). Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) has a negative (-4.599170) relationship with Poverty level (POVR), suggesting that a unit increase in Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) decreases Poverty level (POVR) by 4.599170 units in Nigeria. The negative effect of Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) on Poverty level (POVR) confirm to a priori and therefore is in line with economic theory. The negative effect of Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) on Poverty level (POVR) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) and Poverty level (POVR).

(iii) Long-run Estimation Results for the Model Based on ARDL

The results of the long run estimation of the model is presented in table 5.

Table 5: ARDL Long Run Estimation Result for the Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOG(OREV)	7.430437	4.449370	1.669998	0.1044
INFR	0.072801	0.148379	0.490643	0.6269
LOG(GCEE)	9.026902	8.188519	1.102385	0.2783
COPI	-0.175156	0.311439	-0.562410	0.5776
LOG(GCEH)	-14.254092	8.850192	-1.610597	0.1168
C	12.622249	21.989409	0.574015	0.5698

Source: Author's Computation using E-view Software

From Table 5 the result of the long run estimation shows that Oil Revenue (OREV) has a positive (7.430437) relationship with Poverty level (POVR), suggesting that a unit increase in Oil Revenue (OREV) increases Poverty level (POVR) by 7.430437 units in Nigeria. The positive effect of Oil Revenue (OREV) on Poverty level (POVR) do not confirm to a priori and therefore not in line with economic theory. The positive effect of Oil Revenue (OREV) on Poverty level (POVR) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Oil Revenue (OREV) and Poverty level (POVR).

Inflation (INFR) has a positive (0.072801) relationship with Poverty level (POVR), suggesting that a unit increase in Inflation (INFR) increases Poverty level (POVR) by 0.072801 units in Nigeria. The positive effect of Inflation (INFR) on Poverty level (POVR) confirm to a priori and therefore is in line with economic theory. The positive effect of Inflation (INFR) on Poverty level (POVR) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Inflation (INFR) and Poverty level (POVR) in the long run.

Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) has a positive (9.026902) relationship with Poverty level (POVR), suggesting that a unit increase in Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) increases poverty level (POVR) by 9.026902 units in Nigeria. The positive effect of Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) on Poverty level (POVR) do not confirm to a priori and therefore not in line with economic theory. The positive effect of Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) on poverty level (POVR) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) and poverty level (POVR) in the long run.

Corruption Perception Index (COPI) has a negative (-0.175156) relationship with Poverty level (POVR), suggesting that a unit increase in Corruption Perception Index (COPI) decreases Poverty level (POVR) by 0.175156 units in Nigeria. The negative effect of Corruption Perception Index (COPI) on Poverty level (POVR) do not confirm to a priori and therefore not in line with economic theory. The negative effect of Corruption Perception Index (COPI) on Poverty level (POVR) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Corruption Perception Index (COPI) and Poverty level (POVR) in the long run.

Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) has a negative (-14.254092) relationship with Poverty level (POVR), suggesting that a unit increase in Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) decreases Poverty level (POVR) by 14.254092 units in Nigeria. The negative effect of Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) on Poverty level (POVR) confirm to a priori and therefore in line with economic theory. The positive effect of Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) on Poverty level (POVR) is not statistically significant at 5 percent level. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) and Poverty level (POVR) in the long run.

Post Estimation Test

The researcher conducted a diagnostic test to determine whether or not series were free from order autocorrelation (Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test) and heteroscedasticity (Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Test).

The outcome of the diagnostic tests is presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Ramsey Reset Test, Serial Correlation LM Test and Homoscedasticity Test Results for the Model

	F-Statistic	Prob. Value
Ramsey RESET Test	0.120644	0.7306
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	1.531879	0.2320
Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test	1.549179	0.1559

Source: *Author’s Computation (2024)*

From Table 6, result of autocorrelation test using Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM method showed F-statistics is 1.531879 with a Chi-Square probability value is 0.2320. This indicated that probability value of about 23 percent (0.2320) is larger than 5 percent (0.05) critical value; hence confirmed no serial correlation in model.

Again, result of heteroscedasticity test using Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test showed the F- statistics is 1.549179 and a Chi-Square probability value is 0.1559. This suggested no evidence of heteroskedasticity in model since Chi-square probability value of about 16 percent is more than 5 percent ($p > 0.05$). So, residuals do have constant variance which is desirable in regression denoting that residual are Homoscedastic.

DISCUSSIONS

Oil Revenue (OREV) and Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria

Inferences drawn from both the short run and long run causation using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) estimation shows that Oil Revenue (OREV) reduces Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria in the short run but increases Poverty level (POVR) in the long run; implying that Oil Revenue (OREV) has an unstable effect on Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria. The negative sign of Oil Revenue (OREV) do not conforms to our a priori expectation in the short run but the positive sign of Oil Revenue (OREV) conforms to our a priori expectation in the long run.

Inflation (INFR) and Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria

The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) estimation result shows that Inflation (INFR) increases Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria both in the short run and in the long run; implying that Inflation (INFR) has a stable effect on Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria. The positive sign of Inflation (INFR) conforms to our a priori expectation both in the short run and in the long run.

Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) and Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria.

The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) estimation shows that Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) increases Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria both in the short run and in the long run; implying that Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) has a stable effect on Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria. The positive sign of Oil Revenue (OREV) do not conforms to our a priori expectation both in the short run and in the long run.

Corruption Perception Index (COPI) and Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria

The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) estimation shows that Corruption Perception Index

(COPI) reduces Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria both in the short run and in the long run; implying that Corruption Perception Index (COPI) has a stable effect on Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria. The negative sign of Oil Revenue (OREV) do not conforms to our a priori expectation both in the short run and in the long run.

Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) and Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) estimation shows that Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) reduces Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria both in the short run and in the long run; implying that Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) has a stable effect on Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria. The negative sign of Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) conforms to our a priori expectation both in the short run and in the long run.

CONCLUSION

The study examines empirically the effect of oil revenue on poverty level in Nigeria from 1982 to 2023. In order to achieve this, descriptive statistics, unit root test, bound cointegration, and ARDL estimation method were employed to analyze the data. The study found that Oil Revenue (OREV) reduces Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria in the short run but increases poverty level in the long run in Nigeria. The coefficient of Oil Revenue (OREV) do not impacts significantly on Poverty level (POVR) in Nigeria both in the short run and in the long run; Inflation (INFR) increases Poverty level (POVR) both in the short run and in the long run in Nigeria but do not impact significantly on it; Government Expenditure on Education (GCEE) increases Poverty level (POVR) both in the short run and in the long run in Nigeria but do not impact significantly on it; Corruption Perception Index (COPI) reduces Poverty level (POVR) both in the short run and in the long run in Nigeria but do not impact significantly on it; and Government Expenditure on Health (GCEH) reduces Poverty level (POVR) both in the short run and in the long run in Nigeria but do not impact significantly on it. The study therefore concludes that oil revenue increases poverty level in Nigeria in the long run within the period under review.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should diversify the Economy by investing in Non-Oil Sectors. That is strengthen agriculture, manufacturing, and technology to reduce dependence on oil revenue. Government should support Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) by providing incentives, training, and financial support to diversify income sources for citizens.
2. Government should diversify improve Governance and Transparency by establishing Sovereign Wealth Funds (SWFs) and channel oil revenues into savings or development funds with clear rules for spending.
3. Government should strengthen Anti-Corruption Measures by ensuring that oil revenues are used effectively and equitably by enhancing accountability mechanisms.
4. Government should develop Human Capital by investing in Education. That is Prioritize quality education and skills development to create a workforce capable of thriving in diverse industries.
5. Government should enhance Healthcare Systems. That is improve healthcare access and infrastructure to boost productivity and well-being.

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